

Home Economics Programme as a Tool for Marital Conflict Management

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Abstract: The study investigated Home Economics programme as a tool for marital conflict management. A descriptive survey was used for the study. The population consisted of all members of Home Economics Teachers' Association of Nigeria (HETAN), Ondo State chapter. Sample of one hundred and sixty-three (163) respondents were drawn from the total population using simple random sampling technique. A self-developed structured and validated questionnaire was used for data collection. Data were analyzed using mean. Findings reveal among others lack of trust; parental interference; economic pressure and unrealistic expectation as part of the factors responsible for marital conflict. Findings also revealed mental health issue; inappropriate care for children; communication breakdown and economic instability as part of the implications of inappropriate handling of marital conflict in homes. Furthermore, decision-making process to attain family goals; principles of selection and utilization of family resources and homes and family in a changing world were revealed as part of the contents of Home Economics programme that could help in marital conflicts management. As people consider going for counselling in preparation for marriage, they should also consider taking at least a remedial course in Home Economics to further equip them for stable marital life.

Keywords: Children, Common Conflicts, Conflicts Management, Home Economics Programme, Marital conflicts

1. Introduction

Marital conflicts are common issues in marriage which could be in form of disagreements or misunderstandings between husband and wife. It could also mean the clash, argument or quarrel among others, ensuing between husband and wife. Tolorunleke (2014) defined marital conflicts as the state of tension or stress between marital partners as the couple try to carry out their marital roles. Conflicts are contradictory needs and interests among people. Conflict has been established as a product of interaction between or among people Ohiseghame (2021). Afu and Nteh (2020) opined that, conflicts arise as an attempt to match the behaviour and expectations of one with the behaviour and expectations of the other. Contradictory needs and interest among couple is inevitable and might also be taken as an everyday affaire. According to Amadi and Amadi (2014), crisis is a common feature in every union or association of two or more persons and marriage is not immune to this. Tolorunleke (2014) opined that, since couples are humans and no gods, it is only natural to expect that there will be differences in opinions, values, needs, desires and habits that are the stuff of everyday living. According to Ohiseghame (2021), traditionally conflict is believed to be bad and should be avoided but it is foolhardy to think of a world without conflict because no two persons are the same.

It is however worthy of note that, conflict in marriage on its own is not detrimental to marital satisfaction, but inability of the spouses to appropriately manage the conflict is the actual problem. According to Afu and Uteh (2020), the lingering result of marital conflict usually end up in separation and finally the total collapse, which may be interpreted as liberation but has been viewed by counsellors as a traumatic psychologically difficult condition. Mismanagement of marital conflict should not be allowed to linger. Reason being that, according to Okesina (2022), marriage is the major avenue whereby the society is populated by the number of children that are born into such marriages, thus marital dissatisfaction produces a negative multiplier effect on the society. Relatedly, Tasew and Getahun (2021), marriage, as a basic institution in every society, may be described as one of the important and fundamental human relationships. It is therefore important for every married individual to understand the need for appropriate conflict resolution. Especially as opined by Ostenson and Zhang (2014) that conflicts that are properly managed can help couples learn from each other and improve their relationships.

Most marriages took off beautifully and lovely. To say every individual going into marriage is with the mindset of enjoying the best of it, is never an exaggeration or out of place. But somehow along the line, tide turns and what is meant to be a sweet taste suddenly begin to sour. When this happens, in most cases the cause might be something termed unnecessary or irrelevant. This is to say, just anything could cause conflict in marriage. It could be minor issues such as, Asadi et al. (2016), gathered in a research that, wives believed that, under undesirable life conditions, their husbands used improper phrases to address them. It could also be major issues such as, the findings of Dilder, Sitwat and Yasin (2013), researchers also have identified several major sources of conflict, that is, violent behaviors of husbands, lack of cooperation in the family, inability to spend enough time together, issues related to children and other families, lack of effective communication, and financial problems. According to Tasew and Getahun (2021), the major causes of marital conflict were of psychological, gender related, sexual, socio cultural, economic. However, as common as marital conflict might be termed, many have led and still leading to serious issues in homes, such as violence, abuse, divorce and sometimes death, where there is no appropriate knowledge about how it should be managed. In a study by Tasew and Getahun (2021), five major consequences of marital

conflict were identified to be stress, feeling of depression and grief, worry about what others say beyond the disturbance with their own spouses, and feeling of despair and hopelessness.

Inappropriate management of conflict is becoming more and more rampant in many Nigeria marriages. From the research of Tasew and Getahun (2021), the findings revealed that marital conflict is highly prevalent and showed an increasing trend from year to year. Josiah and Nteh (2022) from experience observe the alarming rate of separation and divorce among spouses in Rivers State. Ondo state is not left out of this saga. According to Olofintoye and Faluyi (2020), it has been observed that many married couples experience marital instability in Nigeria and especially in Ondo State. In this year 2022, in Ondo East local government area of the state, a woman and her son beat the husband to death in the name of the man not catering for the family member enough. This is however dangerous to the society. According to Olaniyi (2015), the family occupies a pivotal place in every in every society and in the Africa continent at large, it is indeed the bedrock of the state, nation, continent and world at large. As earlier stated, it is an established fact that many homes have been managing their conflict in the wrong way. According to Ntoimo and Akokuwebe (2014) the family has been undergoing significant changes in its structure and organization in most countries of the world, prominent among the diverse changes is increase in the number of persons who opt for divorce and mutual or legal separation as alternatives to conflictual marriage. Issues that should have been settled amicably have been allowed to escalate into terrible situations such as suicide or homicide.

Interestingly, Home Economics is a discipline that is design to explicitly cater for all needs and concerns of the family member. Home Economics course contents offer countless ideas to positively manage conflicts in marriages. It can help to positively harness contradictory needs and interest of family members through the numerous interesting course contents. According to Ogbene (2016), Home Economics is aimed at helping people develop desirable social attitude. But in reality, few people have been showing interest in Home Economics Education. Many course contents in Home Economics are specifically designed to develop peaceful homes and to mend where crisis arises. Notable among these are family relationship, family, and marriages. The researchers observed that divorce or separation is rare among Home Economics teachers, not because they married the best behaved husbands, but possibly because of their knowledge of Home Economics. According to Ankoma-Sey, Quansah and Nsoh (2019), the programme of Home Economics is largely described as that body of subject matter which deals with the application of the social and natural sciences together with arts to solving problems in the homes.

1.1. Statement of the Problem

Obviously, it is inevitable for two individual, having different background, different hormone, different temperament among others, signing agreement to become one and staying together (in marriage) under same roof to be clashing once in a while. The clash is however, not the exact issue but its inappropriate management. Some men have turned wife into vehicle particular that should be renewed yearly, they can barely keep a woman under their roof for just two years without marital crisis. The same thing goes for some women that have turned marital home into rented apartment where they can just pack out anytime they are displeased, forgetting the fact that the contract signed is a lifetime. Esere (2008) noted that about forty percent of the marriages contracted every year in Nigeria end up in divorce or separation. From the research of Tasew and Getahun (2021), the findings revealed that marital conflict is highly prevalent and showed an increasing trend

from year to year. The aftermath of inappropriate management of the clash or conflict in marriage might not be problem per se if the two adult (husband and wife) involved are the only one bearing the consequences of their actions, but sadly the product of the union (children) are most times left at the mercy of this disheartening saga. Some of these conflicts are minor issues that should be sorted out amicably if only the husband and the wife have the right knowledge for conflict resolution. However, the good news is that Home Economics programme has more than enough to offer every married individual as well as those intending to go into marriage in term of topnotch marital conflict resolution strategies, hence the research.

1.2. Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of the research is to investigate Home Economics programme as a tool for marital conflicts management. Specific purpose is to:

- a) Identified factors responsible for marital conflict in Ondo state.
- b) Established implications of inappropriate handling of marital conflicts in homes in Ondo state.
- c) Suggest contents of Home Economics programme that could help in marital conflict management in Ondo state.

1.3. Research Questions

The following research question guided the study:

- a) What are the factors responsible for marital conflict in Ondo state?
- b) What are the implications of inappropriate handling of marital conflicts in homes in Ondo state?
- c) What are the contents of Home Economics programme that could help in marital conflict management in Ondo state?

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design for the Study

The design of the study was a Descriptive research design. Descriptive research design was used because it focuses on the vital facts from people, their beliefs, opinions, perception and behavior. According to McCombes (2019), descriptive research aims to accurately and systematically describe a population, situation or phenomenon.

2.1.1. Ethics Statement

The study was approved by the faculty research ethic review committee and carried out with informed oral consent, anonymity and confidentiality of the respondent.

2.2 Area of the Study

The area of the study was Ondo State. Ondo State is one of the states in southwestern Nigeria. It has the land area of 14,788. 723km². The State is made up of 18 local government area. is bounded in the north by Ekiti and Kogi States, in the east by Edo State, in the west by Osun and Ogun states and in the south (Ilaje and Ese-odo) by the Atlantic Ocean. Ondo State is located entirely within the tropics. Apart from the state being peopled predominantly by Yorubas who speak various dialects of the Yoruba language, it also accommodates various ethnic groups across the country, such as Igbo, Hausa and Urhobo among others.

2.3. Population and Sample

The population consisted of all members of Home Economics Teachers Association (HETAN) in Ondo State. Purposive and simple random sampling techniques were used to select one hundred and sixty-three (163) respondents used for the study.

2.4. Instrument for Data Collection

Structure questionnaire was used for data collection. The questionnaire contains four sections ‘A’, ‘B’, ‘C’ and ‘D’. This was formulated based on the 4-points Likert scale type. The response categories for all the sections of the questionnaire were Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree. The instrument was face validated by three experts in the department of Home Economics in Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach’s Alpha procedure as it dealt with multiple score items; it yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.88.

2.5. Data Collection Technique

One hundred and sixty-three (163) copies of the questionnaire were distributed by the researchers, and all were retrieved representing 100% retrieval. 159 copies were appropriately filled which were eventually analyzed.

2.6. Data Analysis Technique

Mean score was used to answer the research questions. Any item with the mean rating of 2.50 (cut-off point = $\frac{4+3+2+1}{5} = \frac{10}{5} = 2.5$) and above was regarded as agreement while anyone with the mean rating of below 2.5 was taken as disagreement.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Research question 1: What are the factors responsible for marital conflicts in Ondo State?

Table 1: Mean responses of the respondents on the factors responsible for marital conflicts in Ondo State

N = 163, COP = 2.50			
S/N	Possible factors responsible for marital conflict.		Decision
1	Sex matter	3.56	Agreed
2	Lack of trust.	3.46	Agreed
3	Parental Interference.	2.98	Agreed
4.	Delay in child bearing	3.02	Agreed
5	Power struggle.	2.78	Agreed
6	Economic pressure	3.58	Agreed
7	Family background	3.43	Agreed
8	Habits such as; clubbing, excessive drug or alcoholic use.	2.62	Agreed
9	Unrealistic expectations	3.58	Agreed
10	Children related problems, such as paying of school fees, feeding or clothing etc.	3.74	Agreed
11	Communication problem.	3.86	Agreed
12	Clash of interest among couple.	3.57	Agreed
13	Maturity in term of age of individual.	2.68	Agreed

Key: N = total number of respondents, COP = cut-off Point, \bar{X} = mean response of all respondents

Table 1 revealed that the mean responses of all the items range from 2.62 to 3.86. This indicates that the respondents agreed with all the items statement as part of the factors responsible for marital conflict in Ondo State because their mean were above the cut-off point of 2.50. The study established the following as some of the factors responsible for marital conflict in Ondo: sex matter; lack of trust; power struggle; delay in child bearing; family background; unrealistic expectations; clash of interest; children related problems such as paying of school fees, feeding or clothing; and communication problem. Obelenienė and Gabševičienė (2015) stated that money, sex, relations, religion and children's education are most pervasive sources of spousal conflict. Asadi, et al (2016) also found that different opinions and perception about issues are part of factors responsible for marital conflicts. Conflicts arise as an attempt to match the behaviour and expectations of one with the behaviour and expectations of the other (Agboola & Oluwatosin, 2018). Ohiseghame (2021) observed in a study that, causes of conflict ranged from infidelity, not giving enough attention, sex, cohesive control, money related matters, distribution of household income neglecting children needs by husbands, and disrespect.

Others include: economic pressure; maturity in term of age of individual; parental interference; habits such as excessive clubbing, smoking, drug use among others and family background. Marital conflict occurs when a husband and wife struggle or have a clash as a result of the pursuant of different goals or needs. Olofintoye and Faluyi (2020) opined that many factors have combined to influence marriage institutions thus causing many problems which both young and old married couples must contend with such as interference by the parents' in-law which could land the relationship in separation or cause threat to its stability. Kadiri and Akinkurolere (2021) pointed that no matter how much a couple can love each other, friction can always be caused by families getting involved. Scott (2020) argued that the stress of fighting over money constitutes one of the most often cited marriage problems that couples face. Ntoimo and Akokuwebe (2014) observed in their research that, prevalence of divorce and separation varies by age. Asadi, et al (2016), dealing with in-laws was a potential source of marital conflict According to Afu and Nteh (2020), in Benue State, problems such as drunkenness, mismanagement of money, poor communication among spouses, domestic violence, infertility among others have cause serious breakdown of a marital relationship. Ohiseghame (2021) notes that it is pertinent to note however that one of the most agreed factor in literature about causes of spousal conflict is money and sex. Josiah and Nteh's (2022) findings showed that parental upbringing, childlessness, lack of financial stability, and religious differences are among the factors responsible for marital disharmony among couples. Okesina (2022) stated that early married men and women may not be matured or well-prepared both physically and emotionally to cope with the demands or the adjustment in marriage.

3.2. Research question 2: What are the implications of inappropriate handling of marital conflicts in homes in Ondo state?

Table 2: Mean responses of the respondents on the implications of inappropriate handling of marital conflicts in homes Ondo State

N = 163, COP= 2.50			
S/N	Possible implications of inappropriate handling of marital conflicts in home.	\bar{X}_3	Decision
1	Mental health issue	3.47	Agreed
2	Extramarital affaire	2.74	Agreed
3	Separation.	3.68	Agreed
4	Communication breakdown.	3.22	Agreed
5	Decline in physical wellbeing	3.35	Agreed
6	Lack of interest in the opposite sex.	2.54	Agreed
7	Economic instability.	2.88	Agreed
8	Inappropriate care for children	3.47	Agreed
9	Divorce	3.80	Agreed
10	Marital violence.	3.76	Agreed

Key: N = total number of respondents, \bar{X} = mean response of all respondents

Table 2 revealed that the mean responses of all the items range from 2.54 to 3.80. This indicates that the respondents agreed with all the items statement as part of the implication of inappropriate handling of marital conflicts in Ondo State because their mean were above the cut-off point of 2.50. When marital conflicts are inappropriately handled or allowed to linger, the study established that, it is most likely to have the following implication in homes: Mental health issue; extramarital affair; separation; communication breakdown in the family; decline in physical wellbeing; lack of interest in the opposite sex; Economics instability; inappropriate care for children; divorce and marital abuse. In this respect, Afu and Uteh (2020) showed that the lingering result of marital conflict usually end up in separation and finally the total collapse. Ohiseghane (2021) observed that unresolved conflict impact negatively on family life, it can lead to dissolution of the union and children suffer in the process. Josiah and Nteh (2022) observed that the consequences of marital conflicts are stress, anxiety, insomnia, suicidal thoughts as well as hatred/fear of the opposite sex.

3.3. *Research question 3:* What are the contents of Home Economics programme that could help in marital conflict management in Ondo state?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation of responses of the respondents on the contents of Home Economics programme that could help in marital conflict management in Ondo State

N = 163, COP= 2.50			
S/N	Possible contents of Home Economics programme that could help in marital conflict management	\bar{X}	Decision
1	Decision making process to attain family goals	3.44	Agreed
2	Principles of selection and utilization of family resources.	3.45	Agreed
3	Appropriate conflict resolution strategies.	3.92	Agreed
4		3.76	Agreed

5	Appropriate communication within the family.	2.75	Agreed
6	Creation of wealth/investment	3.78	Agreed
7	Planning for financial security	3.86	Agreed
8	Interaction among family member	3.04	Agreed
9	Condition for effective family living	3.96	Agreed
10	Important factors in achieving and maintaining successful marriage.	3.42	Agreed
11	Homes and families in a changing world.	2.52	Agreed
12	Family socialization	3.68	Agreed
	Decision making processes in the smooth running of the home.		

Key: N = total number of respondents, C = cut-off Point, \bar{X} = mean response of all respondents

Table 3 revealed that the mean responses of all the items range from 2.52 to 3.92. This indicates that the respondents agreed with all the items statement as part of the possible contents of Home Economics programme that could help in marital conflicts management in Ondo State because their mean were above the cut-off point of 2.50. Home Economics is a programme that is designed to cater for all family affairs. The following are some of the content of Home Economics that will help in appropriate marital conflicts management; decision-making process to attain family goal; Principles of selection and utilization of family resources; appropriate conflict resolution strategies; appropriate communication within the family. According to Okesina (2022), the role communication plays in resolving marital conflict is crucial. Others ways Home Economics programme can help include creation of wealth/investment; planning for financial security; interaction among family member; condition for effective family living; important factors in achieving and maintaining successful marriage; homes and families in a changing world; family socialization; decision making processes in the smooth running of the home. According to Ode (2013), Home Economics is the study of all that relate to home and family. Uwameiye (2015), Home Economics is a field of knowledge which is skill-based and is primarily concerned with strengthening families, conducting researches to discover changing needs of individuals and families and the means of satisfying these needs. For Alabi and Keswet (2015), Home Economics is a field of study that is primarily concerned with strengthening family life and increasing productivity of individuals in the social economy. As per McGregor (2019) assertion, home economists can be effective change agents acting as catalysts between families and governments. Ogunmosin, Akinyotu and Orisamika (2021) noted that Home Economics is the study of activities that relates to the home and the family; it is a field of study that is concerned with improving and strengthening family life. The result of this study has implication on all individual, both married and about to be married. It was clear from the study that marital conflict in marriages are inevitable and inappropriate handling of the conflicts has been leading to serious crisis among couples. Similar study can be carried out to in other state of the country or in another country.

4. Conclusion

Conflict is inevitable wherever two or more people are involved, which marriage of course is one of the focal points. However, every individual should rightly understand that conflict itself is not supposed to be a serious issue. The exact issue is when it is not properly managed and allowed to

degenerate into crisis. Good knowledge in home economic programme can adequately equip every individual to positively manage any form of conflict they are facing or likely to encounter in their marriage. Every individual should bear in mind that, there is hardly any conflict happening in their marriage that has not, is not or will not happen in another's. As a result, they should not because of common conflict call it quit or do anything irrational in marriage. Nobody should see his or herself as a perfect one in marriage, as it is possible for your spouse to offend you, so it is for you to also offend your spouse. So learn to let go or seek redress where necessary. Every married individual should put it at the back of their mind that children are also stake holders in marital affairs, so their interest should be considered before allowing common conflict to degenerate into serious crisis. As people consider going for counselling in preparation for marriage, they should also consider taking at least a remedial course in Home Economics to further equip them for stable marital life.

Acknowledgements

The authors are very grateful to all Home Economics teachers who gave their informed consent and responds to this study. The authors are equally grateful to the validators who helped to modify the instrument as well as the reviewers and the journal editor for their unalloyed hard work and constructive suggestions which enabled the improvement of the quality of the paper.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization: AOL, JOO, OWA

Final Analysis: AOL, JOO

Funding acquisition: AOL, JOO, OWA

Investigation: OWA, AOL, JOO

Methodology: JOO, AOL, OWA

Writing- Original draft, review & editing: AOL, JOO, OWA

Data Availability Statement

The original contributors presented in the study are included in the article. Further enquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

Funding Information

The authors have no funding to disclose.

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Publisher: Department of Home Economics and Hospitality Management Education, University of Nigeria, Nsukka 41001, Nigeria

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